

Services and Recommendations for your Research Data

Our digital research data in the historically oriented humanities consists of *historical records* that are selected, gathered, annotated, compared, contextualized and represented in digital formats.

Your research data is important. You spend a lot of time and energy to collect, create, analyze and interpret it. **The IEG supports you in securing and enhancing your data.** The institute provides infrastructure and we, the *DH Lab* of the IEG, offer help and support in finding suitable solutions. Essentially, we want to recommend and offer you four things:

1. Start early:

- Make a *data management plan* for your digital research material.
- Consider how you will store, explain and share it.
- **We offer you advice and support.**

2. Secure it:

- What would happen if you lose your data?
It is of uttermost importance to have a backup.
- Have “a backup for your backup” with the 3-2-1 rule: three copies, on two mediums, and one copy off-site.
- **We offer you infrastructure and good practices.**

3. Enhance it:

- Collecting and organizing digital assets is challenging, but suitable workflows and tools may help.
- Proper data management can improve research efficiency and scientific value of your data.
- **We offer you ideas and joint efforts.**

4. Provide it:

- Consider your data as valuable even after your primary research: As a scholarly publication, it gets reused, cited and reputable.
- Publishing your data requires additional documentation effort, open licenses, standard file formats, and a trustworthy publisher.
- **We offer you consulting and editorial work.**

Setting up bibliographies, collecting sources, modelling historical concepts, training in tools and techniques – discuss your needs and ideas with us. Our *Research Data Manager* is looking forward to hear your questions, issues and plans: Fabian Cremer, cremer@ieg-mainz.de – start early!

Please note the “Guideline for handling research data at the IEG”:

Short link: purl.org/ieg/rdm

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